

"MOLECULAR LEAF"

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Abstract. The article discusses climate change and its problems and today's solutions, the importance of chemical preparations produced by chemical industry enterprises in industrial development, and the harmful aspects to the environment and animals.

A molecule that can be a source of clean energy has been synthesized. Do you notice that climate changes are becoming more and more evident on our planet. This forces scientists to struggle with the issue of developing clean energy sources that are safe for the entire planet's climate and biosphere. Of course, you already know well about some practical scientific and technical achievements in this direction. After all, nobody can be surprised today with energy sources such as wind turbines and solar panels. But when it comes to clean energy sources, there is an area that is less talked about and almost not disclosed to the general public, and in the near future, it is this area that can make a revolutionary turn as a source of clean and cheap energy. The alternative, clean, low-cost energy source we're talking about is called the "molecular leaf." According to the idea of scientists, this "leaf" should artificially repeat the process of photosynthesis, which is the main energy converter in nature. In short, scientists want to invent substances and materials that will artificially carry out the process of photosynthesis. That is, we are not wrong to say that it will be an artificial leaf. But there is no guarantee that its appearance will exactly repeat the ordinary leaf and leaves that we know.

The idea is very simple: through artificial photosynthesis, scientists want to use solar energy to convert carbon dioxide (CO₂) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) into fuel. . The most advanced scientific research in this direction is currently being conducted at the Indiana University of the USA by a research group led by Professor Liang-shi Lee. In an article published in the Journal of the American Chemical Society in March of this year, the leader of the scientific group spoke about this alternative energy source. emphasized. Carbon dioxide and carbon dioxide are actually abundant in the atmosphere. As a result of excessive accumulation of these gases, the "greenhouse effect" will occur on the planet

Earth, and as a result, the climate will change drastically, the temperature will rise, the ice ages will melt, and eventually the level of the world's ocean will rise, and most of the land will be covered. There have long been legitimate concerns about the occupation. Unfortunately, these concerns are slowly becoming reality these days, and the satellite images clearly show this. From this point of view, the "molecular leaf" technology can be of great importance not only as a source of cheap and clean energy, but also in reducing the amount of greenhouse gases (CO and CO₂) in the atmosphere. Professor Lian-shi Lee's scientific group proposes to use a molecular complex based on nanographene and rhenium to convert atmospheric greenhouse gases into fuel by means of a "molecular leaf". In this case, the nanographene absorbs the energy of the Sun's rays, and then the electrons pass to the rhenium atoms. Rhenium atoms bind carbon oxides in the atmosphere. Moreover, natural sunlight is not necessary for the reaction to proceed. Unlike natural leaves, the molecular leaf can photosynthesize from the light of an electric lamp. According to calculations, a voltage of only 0.48 V is enough for the reaction to start. It should be noted that this indicator is the lowest for catalysts of this type known to us so far. The scientific group is limited to note that initial achievements in this direction have been noted. However, if you pay attention to some comments at the end of the article, it seems that artificial photosynthesis has already been implemented at Indiana University.

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